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Definition and application of process tools for rib structure design in Large-scale additive manufacturing

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Abstract: This paper introduces an innovative approach to large-format robotic additive manufacturing (LFRAM) by implementing a parametric point array patterning (PAP) method within Rhino Grasshopper. Unlike conventional slicing algorithms that convert 3D models into layers, the proposed solution generates toolpath sequences directly from parametric models. The methodology leverages integrated Grasshopper components to create customizable ribbed structures with adjustable dimensions and spacing, offering enhanced flexibility for large-scale applications. Experimental validation was performed using a FANUC M-20iB/25 industrial robot equipped with a pellet extruder, with PETG selected for manufacturing a structural component measuring 1500 × 100 × 60 mm. Several calibration samples confirmed the feasibility of the PAP method and its scalability for complex geometries. The results demonstrate validity of proposed method and critically highlight the challenges ahead. However, further refinement is required to address issues such as material overlap at rib intersections and building plate adhesion. This research highlights the potential of parametric modeling and robotic AM in advancing additive manufacturing for industrial-scale applications.

Keywords: LFRAM, Grasshopper, slicing, parametric design, visual scripting

1. Introduction

Currently, 3D printers are being utilized for prototyping and developing new products. The appeal of this solution mostly stems from its capability to facilitate the additive manufacturing (AM) of three-dimensional items featuring intricate geometries [1].

A crucial step in the AM process is the division of the model into layers, commonly referred to as slicing [2]. However, the well-known solutions in this area are mainly dedicated to classic 3D printers and their manufacturing specifications, therefore do not fully support the process of large format robotic additive manufacturing (LFRAM) [3–5] which brings challenges to overcome in the form of technological requirements for material processing that must be considered. The challenges lie not only in the requirement to produce large components, where conventional 3D printers reach their limits in terms of printing space and flexibility, but also in optimizing current manufacturing processes in order to speed them up, reduce their costs and gain full control over the entire process. One of those challenges is tool path movement control. With the large amount of material that the print head needs to process, it is sometimes difficult to ensure proper retraction or suspension of material extrusion for infill strategies offered by classic slicer software and

therefore, the only way to optimize such production is to properly design and control tool path movement so that such retractions or suspensions are not necessary at all [6-8].

In order to demonstrate such approach, a script in Rhino software within Grasshopper plugin (RGP) was created that demonstrates how such tool path movement can be designed for example, for the purpose of creating building or facade structures where conventional infill strategies are replaced with ribbed ones that could be quickly edited with possibility to generate customized unconventional infills instructions, where no Computer aided design (CAD) model is needed and additionally one continual tool path movement is generated. In response to the challenges noted, a novel solution is presented which employs a parametric model of the prototyped and manufactured component to directly generate control code ready to postprocess for LFRAM. Methodologies related to LFRAM are discussed in section 2, with a specific focus on the slicing stage of the process where new point array patterning method is presented. Section 3 presents a description and the assumptions of the proposed solution, dedicated to experimental verification of developed system.

2. Materials and Methods

To generate such movement a grasshopper script capable of the point array patterning (PAP) method was created and used. Instead of a common slicing algorithm that transforms 3D objects into individual layers, the grasshopper script allows to create sequences of points which represent positions and orientations of the tool center point (TCP) directly. The Grasshopper PAP script (fig. 1) was developed to generate G-code for a simple ribbed structure to verify functionality of this approach. To achieve this, several integrated function blocks and special position obtaining blocks of Rhino Grasshopper software were used.

Figure 1. Grasshopper PAP script.

The Grasshopper PAP script consists of 5 sections, which are parametrically connected and convert Input data into printable G code. Section A (fig. 1) collects input data as general dimensions of structure, layer height, number of ribs, ribs spacing, and more. Section B (fig. 1) is generating and patterning points in a simplified 2D grid block function where the sequence of the points are specified. Plotting of the distance of the points (Section C.) serves as an aid for the user to verify the final dimensions and can be deactivated for a detailed view of the structure layers. In section D (fig. 1), points and layers are generated, and the condition of the layer printing order is specified. The curves created by connecting patterned points serve as layer indicators and are displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Graphical preview of PAP script with different input data combinations.

Final points coordination representing the tool path movement order is obtained in section D. The results of the grasshopper script (Section D) can then be exported in G-code format. Once the G-code has been generated, it must be uploaded into the robot simulating software RoboDK. This is where the robot's movement is programmed and the G-code is translated into the robot's movement language. The final steps of the preprocessing of robotics 3D printing include setting up start/end procedures, final checking for possible collisions, and uploading the program to the robot. The experiment was conducted on a FANUC M-20iB/25 robot equipped with an MDPH2 pellet extruder.

Figure 3. Simulation of PAP script in RoboDK CAM software.

3. Results

Offline programming and simulation of the robot's movements was done in specialized RoboDK software for industrial robots with 3D printing plugin. Translated robot language was transferred to the control system of the robot and then executed. The script tests the PAP method as approach to design unique structures in the field of large-scale additive manufacturing. Several samples were printed for validation of method functionality.

Table 1. Material and input data combination for calibration samples.

Sample	Material	Printing speed [mm/s]	Layer height [mm]	Nozzle temperature [C°]
A	PETG	25	2	215
B	ABS	20	1,5	230
C	PP	20	1,5	200

Different materials as PETG, ABS and PP where used in combination of input data setting which were tested to find proper combination settings to ensure material extrusion and overall manufacturing process stability. Samples A, B and C were printed with overall dimension of 250 x 50x 30 mm

Figure 4. Calibration samples.

After initial calibration of input data and materials, PETG material was chosen for the manufacturing of a large structural part of overall dimensions 1500 x 100 x 60 mm. In figure 5 where shape warpage, are presented and detailed in section A and B.

Figure 5. Large Scale ribbed structure.

4. Conclusions

The printed samples proved that the designed script works. Calibration samples were printed to determine input manufacturing data for chosen materials. The use of the Rhi-noceros Grasshopper software extends the possibilities of designing the toolpath to create unique ribbed structures with customized dimension and ribs spacing options. Manufacturing large scale ribbed structure verified the scalability of the created PAP script however, further optimization is necessary to prevent material layer overlapping in areas where ribs are connected. Also Build plate adhesion must be improved by redesigning build plate to be able to physically anchor parts to prevent warping.

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